

AXIAL LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY OF GLASSFIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC LONG TUBULAR MEMBERS

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ABSTRACT

When slender composite structural members with hollow section are used as columns for structural applications, buckling becomes a main consideration in the design. A particular application of tubular conical columns is their use as cable supports by telephone and electric companies. With regard to this application, buckling is mainly connected to corner poles which are guyed, in order to prevent excessive lateral deflections due to the transversal component of the cable tension. Hence, these members are subjected to compression and bending, the amplitude of the axial load depending on the transversal force and the guy inclination.

In this paper results of an experimental and analytical investigation on the behaviour of glassfibre reinforced plastic (GRP) tapered poles with circular hollow section subjected to axial loading are presented. After an experimental research aimed to describe the mechanical characteristics and to perform a quality control of the glassfibre reinforced plastic material adopted in fabrication of these tubular members, a number of full scale tests were performed on 9 meters long tapered poles within a testing facility set up in co-operation with the Structural Engineering Department of Politecnico di Milano.

By means of a numerical model calibrated on the experimental results, an analytical investigation was also performed to predict the non linear response of the pole and a parametric study was carried out considering the effect of the main parameters governing the problem.

INTRODUCTION

Glass-fibre reinforced plastic tapered columns are being extensively used for supporting light weights such as cables, lamps, antennas, etc. A particular application of GRP tubular conical columns is their use as cable supports by telephone and electric companies. Many advantages such as light self weight, high corrosion resistance and the mass production (as well as the technical improvements achieved in the last two decades) make composite materials convenient with respect to conventional ones (like wood, steel or concrete) from an economical point of view. Since 1984, GRP centrifugated poles have been used in Italy to support overhead lines. With regard to this application, buckling is mainly connected to the corner poles of the lines which are guyed, in order to prevent excessive lateral deflections due to the transversal component of the cable tension. Hence, these members, are subjected to compression and bending; the amplitude of the axial load depends on the transversal force and the guy inclination. The poles are driven in the ground for nearly $1.3 \div 1.5$ m, and the guys are connected nearly 0.5 m below the top section. As the

production procedures of these poles are such that the glass fibre content vary along the longitudinal axis of the member, an experimental investigation and quality control of the mechanical properties of the material started in 1990, by the Laboratory of Tests and Materials of the Structural Engineering Department of Politecnico di Milano.

In the study, attention was concentrated on poles having a truncated conical shape, 9 meters long; the maximum external diameter at the pole base is equal to 250 mm and the minimum external diameter at the top section is equal to 115 mm. The wall thickness is 7.0 ± 0.5 mm. All the poles possess a perfectly smooth external surface and thus qualify at the 1st level of ASTM 2563-70 rules. Furthermore, the external surface is overlaid with a special non woven fabric, which guarantees protection against UV rays and environmental chemical attacks.

The first phase of the study was aimed to characterise the mechanical behaviour of the material; tests to evaluate the Young's modulus and tensile as well as compressive resistance were performed on specimens and full scale stubs. Furthermore, 2 meters long specimens cut from the columns were used for four points bending tests.

Results from the first testing phase are illustrated in a different paper [1, 2]; they provided important information to perform structural analysis herein discussed such as the statistical distribution of the Young modulus, of tensile and compression strength and of wall thickness.

The second phase of the research, herein illustrated, dealt with the axial load carrying capacity of these members. Full scale tests were carried out on 9 m long poles to analyse the behaviour of these members under working conditions. For long composite columns, overall buckling is more likely to occur before any other instability failure and the anisotropic nature of the material has to be accounted for. Because of the large elongation to failure allowed by both the fibres and the resin, the composite material behaviour is linear elastic under large deflections (and strains) unlike conventional materials that yield (steel) or crack (concrete) for moderate strains. Therefore buckling is the governing failure mode of these members.

Several full scale tests were carried out; afterwards a numerical simulation of the pole response was performed by means of a non-linear Finite Element Method [3] structural analysis. This paper describes the results of experimental buckling tests carried out on full scale poles simulating the working conditions and discusses the comparison between experimental and numerical simulation results.

A brief parametric study was carried out by means of the numerical model previously calibrated on the experimental results; the influence of

- thickness
- initial out of straightness
- guy inclination

on the load carrying capacity of these members is presented and discussed.

MATERIAL IDENTIFICATION AND QUALITY CONTROL

Concerning the working conditions of GRP tapered poles, the Italian Telephon Company defined technical recommendations about mechanical properties that should be adopted by the different producers working in different locations on national territory. The leading requirements were aimed to the attainment of a uniform quality of the product: the mean thickness equal to 7 mm, a characteristic value for tensile strength greater than 160 MPa and a characteristic value for the modulus of elasticity greater than 20000 MPa. Furthermore, the poles, produced with unsaturated (thermosetting) polyester resins, E-glass fibres and fabrics, must guarantee protection against UV and chemical attacks.

A quality control plan was developed to meet these requirements; tensile tests were carried out on small specimens to evaluate Young's Modulus and tensile strength and four points bending tests were performed on two meters long specimens to study flexural properties like bending strength and flexural modulus of elasticity. Various firms producing and installing poles all over the Italian National territory were controlled. A good agreement was obtained between Young's modulus values got from tensile and bending tests for the various firms [2]. The main results of this quality

control study are presented in Table 1, where mean values (E_m), characteristic values (E_b) and standard deviation (S) for Young's modulus are illustrated.

Table 1

FIRM	TENSILE			COMPRESSION			BENDING		
	E_{mT} (MPa)	E_{bT} (MPa)	S_T (MPa)	E_{mC} (MPa)	E_{bC} (MPa)	S_C (MPa)	E_{mB} (MPa)	E_{bB} (MPa)	S_B (MPa)
A	26495	21175	2700	17011	12975	1345	22762	19451	1850
B	23384	20383	1436	20716	13532	2395	20486	19550	529
C	25230	22640	1282	20093	12956	2379	20500	19406	618
D	22586	20241	782	20691	12389	2768	21588	20318	572
E	22616	16817	2416	21333	16423	1637	22923	21572	764
F	22944	19669	1621	20552	13865	2229	19765	18825	531

All the poles were made by centrifugal casting, a production technique for fabricating cylindrical and conical shapes in which glass-fibre mats and roving are positioned inside a hollow mandrel designed to be heated and rotated as resin is cured [4]. The internal side of the mandrel reproduces the external shape of the product. By controlling step by step the angular velocity - slow rotational velocity during the resin filling and a faster velocity during the curing - and the resin viscosity - mainly operating on the mandrel temperature -, it is possible to get a well impregnated fabric with an almost constant thickness; the tested poles, had a thickness varying between 6.5 and 7.5 millimetres. A statistical analysis of specimen thickness variation was performed resulting in a mean value of 7.15 mm with a standard deviation of 1.17 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The experimental study was performed on 9 m high poles. They were tested in horizontal position in order to make easier the loading application and the specimen set up during the testing operations. Of course, due to such a choice, the pole's self weight imposed an initial out of straightness to the member (that could eventually be reduced by pretensioning of the guys) resulting in aestimates of the load carrying capacity on the safe side. The testing machine was specifically built to test a pole fixed at the one end and stabilised with a couple of guys 7.587 m long connected to the pole's top and to the machine. Two steel truss towers 2.5 m high connected at the top by a steel beam were built to fix the two steel guys. The pole has a total length of 9 m and it is fixed in correspondence of its base section (the one with the largest diameter) by clamps to a concrete foundation. The experimental configuration is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 - Testing equipment

Volume V: Structures

The pole span from the fixing support to the load application point is equal to 7.135 m. Thanks to the horizontal position of the pole, a vertical hydraulic jack was used to apply the load which represents, together with the pole weight, the effects of wind and cable tension. The hydraulic jack was positioned inside a hole and was connected to a dynamometer which permitted to know, step by step, the value of the applied load. A steel clamp was used to connect the guys to the pole and to transmit the load from the hydraulic jack to the pole end. A glass mat was introduced between the pole and the steel clamp to increase friction and to contrast sliding.

Guy forces are directly applied to the clamp, requiring a very accurate installation to avoid displacements between the pole and the clamp and to get a centred load application preventing bending effects in planes different from the load-axis/pole-axis plane. Furthermore, a linear variable differential transformer (LVDTs) was used for monitoring the pole deflection at the jack. Hence, because of the guy forces, the pole is subjected to compression and bending. The high axial force and the pole slenderness can cause structural collapse for global buckling instead of material failure.

Each specimen was monitored to investigate forces, displacements and strain values in the most significative points to get information about the pole resistance under working loads. By three dynamometers the load and the guy forces were measured while the transversal load was incremented. An LVDT was applied to measure the deflection of the pole end and it was positioned as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 - Testing equipment

Six strain gages were used to get the strain distribution; the four strain gages, positioned on opposite pole sides near the end section, provided information about axial and bending actions while the two strain gages positioned near the load application point, where bending is negligible, provided information about axial load.

A preliminary test under a cyclic load was performed to evaluate pole elastic behaviour and testing repeatability under different load levels. Fig. 3 plots the experimental values of jack-load vs jack-displacement; the unloading slope is equal to the loading one and the permanent displacement at the end of the first cycle is nearly 2 mm. Such a small permanent deflection compared to the dimensions of the testing specimen (0.03% of the total length), means that, for whole testing duration, the pole remains in the elastic field.

Figure 3 - Jack load vs. deflection diagram

Afterwards several tests were performed on poles; hereafter, results concerning a typical test are presented and discussed.

The load application was quasi-static and it increased up to the critical load; when the top deflection reached 160 mm, the LVDT was removed in order to avoid damage. The pole response up to buckling was linear elastic and no external damage was observed. A typical deformed shape after global buckling of the specimen is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 - a) undeformed; b) buckling

Between jack load, F_j , and guy forces, F_{g1} and F_{g2} , the following relationship can be derived from equilibrium considerations:

$$F_j = (F_{g1} + F_{g2}) \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot \sin \beta \quad (1)$$

where α and β are the angles shown in Fig. 2.

By equilibrium relationship, the axial load P can be desumed:

$$P = (F_{g1} + F_{g2}) \cdot \cos \beta \quad (2)$$

Strain gage results provided the diagram of Fig. 5, where measured values are reported by load.

Figure 5 - Strain gages readings

From the diagram appears that the maximum elongation was detected by the strain gages named 0 and 1 whose positioned near the load application point where, because of pole shape, the section has a smaller area than near the base section.

The elongation values measured by strain gages 2, 3, 4 and 5 provide information about the pole bending in planes $x-y$ and $x-z$. Initially, in load plane $x-y$ the upper fibres are subjected to tension as positive values recorded by the strain gage 4 show. While the load increases, mainly because of the particular pole deformed shape, the lower fibres become subjected to tension as illustrated from strain gage 5. In the $x-z$ plane the maximum compressed fibres are on the z -axis negative side (strain gage 3).

The stiffness of the experimental set up was also monitored by means of LVDTs and the top displacements of the steel towers (to which the guys were connected) measured under testing. The recorded values, however, turned out to be negligible.

NON-LINEAR STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS BY FEM

The behaviour of the guyed pole was simulated by means of the FEM code STRAND6 release 6.1 (1994), by G+D Computing Pty Ltd [3].

A linear buckling analysis was initially performed, in order to evaluate the Euler critical load for the member. Later on, a non linear (large displacements) static analysis was performed considering geometrical non linearities. The member was simulated by means of 18 finite "beam" elements, considering the variation of both the geometrical properties as well as the Young's modulus, along the longitudinal axis. In particular, based on the results of the quality analysis previously described, the Young's modulus was assumed to vary between 23000 MPa at the bottom section and 20000 MPa at the top. The boundary conditions were introduced as fixities in the lower nodes, in order to simulate the real working conditions of the member which is driven in the ground for nearly $1.3 \div 1.5$ meters. The guys were simulated as cable members, with 10 mm diameter and a Young's modulus of 130000 MPa.

COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 6 shows, for a typical test, the jack load plotted vs. the guy force. The nominal relationship - represented by Eqn. (1) - is also plotted in the same figure as well as results from FEM simulation.

Figure 6 - Numerical-experimental comparison for jack load-guy force

Fig. 7 shows correlation between transversal load applied by hydraulic jack and axial load inside the pole. The nominal axial load, given by equation (2), the experimental values obtained by strain gages 0-5 readings and the FEM results are shown. The Young's modulus adopted in deriving the axial load values from strain gage measures, was obtained by tensile tests on specimens taken by the pole itself. Because of irregular glass-fibre mat distribution the values of the modulus of elasticity are different for sections at different levels on the pole axis; based on previous tests, the Young modulus was assumed equal to 23000 MPa for sections in correspondence of S-2 to S-5 gages and equal to 19600 MPa for sections monitored by S-0 and S-1 gages. The response of the GRP material was assumed to be linear elastic to failure.

Figure 7 - Numerical-experimental comparison for jack load-axial load

An excellent correlation can be observed between measured values, numerical simulation ones and the nominal load given by Eqn. (2).

EFFECTS OF VARIATION OF MAIN GEOMETRICAL PARAMETERS ON LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY

By FEM analysis, a sensitivity study was performed applying geometrical variations on the numerical model. A 34.9 kN mean value for the buckling load was detected for undeformed pole; initial deformed shapes were assigned to poles for studying the P_b dependence from geometrical imperfections; results are reported in Tab. 2 where P_b is listed as function of geometrical imperfections applied to the pole top section according to Fig. 2.

Table 2

P_b [kN]	imperfection in x-z plane (z dir.) [mm]	imperfection in x-y plane (y dir.) [mm]
34.92	-	-
34.78	-	+ 20
35.05	-	- 20
36.19	-	- 40
34.91	+ 20	-
35.05	+ 20	- 20

P_b increases as the imperfection in the x-y plane (-y direction) increases; as a matter of fact it means that the guys inclination on the x-axis increases. New FEM runs were performed varying guys inclination from 15° to 25° getting buckling loads for the two limit configurations respectively equal to 26.8 kN and 46.9 kN. From previously described quality control on the material a pole thickness variation equal to about 0.5 mm occurred for specimens under testing; a further numerical simulation was then performed assuming a pole wall thickness of 7.5 mm. The buckling load appeared to be increased of about 3.9 % with respect to the 7 mm wall thickness. From the analysis it can be concluded that the guys' inclination on the longitudinal member axis is the main parameter governing buckling of these members. An initial out of straightness results in an increased angle between guys and x-axis and in a larger buckling load.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental and analytical investigation of the buckling load of a full-size GRP pole have been described. The data from experimental analysis have been compared with predictions obtained from an analytical model. The numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental data. The guys inclination with the x-axis have been identified as having a major influence on the buckling load. Wall thickness and Young's modulus play a considerably minor role in buckling phenomena of these poles.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research, as part of a Finalised Project on Special Materials for Advanced Technologies, was carried out with the financial support of the Italian Research Council (CNR).

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